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US Human Milk Storage Practices and Challenges Survey

n = >1,000 respondents (National Representation)

SUMMARY

Your age? ...

Q2

What is your estimated household income? ...

Q3

1981 of 2013 answered

Counts

\$0-\$19,999	19%	378
\$20,000-\$49,999	32%	633
\$50,000-\$99,999	30%	585
\$100,000-\$199,999	13%	264
\$200,000+	4%	71
Not sure	1%	19
Prefer not to answer	2%	31

In what state do you live? ...

Q4

1972 of 2013 answered	Counts
Alabama	3% 55
Alaska	1% 10
Arizona	2% 43
Arkansas	1% 26
California	7% 137
Colorado	1% 26
Connecticut	1% 17
Delaware	0% 4
Florida	7% 143
Georgia	4% 88
Hawaii	0% 6
Idaho	1% 10
Illinois	4% 71
Indiana	3% 51
Iowa	1% 20
Kansas	1% 16
Kentucky	2% 38
Louisiana	2% 30
Maine	0% 4
Maryland	2% 32
Massachusetts	1% 28
Michigan	4% 70
Minnesota	1% 22
Mississippi	2% 33

1972 of 2013 answered	Counts
Missouri	3% 56
Montana	0% 3
Nebraska	1% 16
Nevada	1% 23
New Hampshire	0% 4
New Jersey	2% 30
New Mexico	0% 8
New York	5% 99
North Carolina	4% 72
North Dakota	0% 4
Ohio	5% 101
Oklahoma	1% 29
Oregon	1% 15
Pennsylvania	5% 100
Rhode Island	0% 8
South Carolina	2% 40
South Dakota	0% 2
Tennessee	3% 55
Texas	9% 183
Utah	1% 15
Vermont	0% 0
Virginia	2% 48
Washington	1% 28
West Virginia	1% 21
Wisconsin	1% 26
Wyoming	0% 2
District of Columbia	0% 4

Please select the race(s) or ethnic group(s) you consider yourself to be a part of. You may select more than one option. ...

Q5

1964 of 2013 answered		Counts
American Indian or Alaska Native	2%	47
Asian	5%	92
Black or African American	27%	525
Hispanic or Latino	15%	304
Middle Eastern or North African (MENA)	1%	15
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	1%	22
White	58%	1135
Prefer not to answer	0%	8
Other (key in)	1%	16

Show other values

What is your current employment status?

Q6

1858 of 2013 answered		Counts
Full-time employed	43%	795
Part-time employed	19%	357
Unemployed	24%	449
Student (whether also full or part-time employed)	4%	80
Retired	1%	11
Prefer not to answer or not applicable	3%	47
Other (key in)	6%	119

Show other values

Do you have a child under 10?

Q7

1962 of 2013 answered		Counts
Yes	86%	1695

1962 of 2013 answered

Counts

No 14% 267

What year was your baby born? If you have multiple children under 10, what year was your youngest born? ...

Q8

1692 of 2013 answered

Counts

2015	2%	26
2016	1%	19
2017	1%	23
2018	2%	32
2019	11%	188
2020	15%	257
2021	14%	243
2022	20%	343
2023	22%	369
2024	11%	192

Answer the remaining questions in this survey to the best of your knowledge. If you have more than one child, answer based on your most recent experience. ...

Q9

How is/was your baby fed during the first 6 months of life?

1403 of 2013 answered		Counts
Breastmilk, exclusively	38%	538
Formula, exclusively	22%	310
Combination of formula and breastmilk	40%	555

Did you ever attempt to breastfeed? ...

Q10

310 of 2013 answered		Counts
Yes	62%	191
No	38%	119

The remainder of this survey is about breastmilk storage practices. Would you be comfortable commenting on the breastfeeding part of your feeding experience? ...

Q11

191 of 2013 answered		Counts
Yes, I would	94%	179
No	6%	12

When breastmilk was used, in what manner was it given to the baby? ...

Q12

1093 of 2013 answered		Counts
The breastmilk was given exclusively at the breast	29%	316
The breastmilk came from exclusively pumped milk	19%	203

1093 of 2013 answered	Counts
A combination of breast- and pumped milk	51% 560
Other (e.g. milk bank, community share)	1% 7
I do not remember	1% 7

Have you stored breastmilk?

Q13

1272 of 2013 answered	Counts
Yes, I have stored my breastmilk	83% 1055
No, I have not stored my breastmilk	17% 217

What percentage of breastmilk do or did you store?

Q14

1056 of 2013 answered	Counts
25% (or "some")	39% 412
50% (or "about half")	41% 428
75% (or "most")	13% 135
100% (or "all")	6% 63
I do not remember	2% 18

How have you most commonly stored expressed breastmilk?

Q15

1056 of 2013 answered		Counts
At room temperature	10%	108
Refrigerator	64%	677
Freezer	68%	723
I do not remember	0%	3
Other (key in)	0%	2

Show other values

If you have stored breastmilk in the freezer, what was your reason for freezing breastmilk? ...

Q16

722 of 2013 answered		Counts
Work	38%	272
Travel	23%	163
Oversupply	63%	453
Daycare	24%	176
Other (key in)	9%	66

Show other values

What is the average amount of time you have stored expressed breastmilk in the freezer? ...

Q17

721 of 2013 answered		Counts
Less than 1 month	31%	224
1-3 months	40%	285
4-6 months	17%	123
More than 6 months	12%	89

Have you ever noticed any changes in your frozen breastmilk after defrosting? ...

Q18

719 of 2013 answered

Counts ▾

Yes, change in smell	13%	93
Yes, change in taste	6%	45
Yes, both change in taste and smell	10%	71
No changes detected	69%	499
Other (key in)	2%	11

Show other values

If you stored your breastmilk in the refrigerator, how long have you stored it before feeding it to your baby? ...

Q19

303 of 2013 answered

Counts ▾

Less than 24 hours	56%	170
1 to 3 days	40%	121
3 to 5 days	3%	9
More than 5 days	1%	3
Other (key in)	0%	0

Show other values

Have you ever noticed any changes in your breastmilk after storing in the refrigerator? ...

Q20

303 of 2013 answered		Counts
Yes, change in smell	14%	41
Yes, change in taste	7%	21
Yes, both change in taste and smell	10%	30
No changes detected	68%	205
Other (key in)	2%	6

Show other values

Did your baby accept or reject the stored milk?

Q21

1003 of 2013 answered		Counts
Accepted (same as fresh milk)	70%	702
Sometimes rejected (or accepted but with more difficulty than fresh milk)	23%	235
Rejected	3%	34
Did not attempt to feed	2%	17
I do not remember	1%	15

Have you ever discarded stored breastmilk?

Q22

1050 of 2013 answered		Counts
Yes, frequently	21%	220
Yes, once or twice	53%	561
No, never	26%	269

If you have discarded breastmilk, what was the reason?

Q23

781 of 2013 answered

Counts

Storage was in question (e.g. power outage, freezer left open, etc.)	38%	293
Baby did not finish the feeding	62%	486
The milk smelled off	23%	180
Other (key in)	5%	40

Show other values